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SOCIAL INNOVATIONS IN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITIES: COMMUNITY-BUILDING – AN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

There is unanimous agreement within the technical sciences on the importance of engineering for societal development. Sensitizing engineers to the challenges of our society and to inter- and transdisciplinary collaboration is important for modern engineering education. The paradigm of Responsible Research and Innovation is ubiquitous in funding agencies and research institutions as well as universities. Social responsibility is understood as the foundation for excellent research and teaching. Based on this, RWTH Aachen University understands the potential of innovative, socially responsible engineering education to meet new challenges. Therefore, the "Responsible Research and Innovation Hub" (RRI Hub) was founded in 2019, based on the concept of the integrated and interdisciplinary university.² The aim is to establish an extensive collaboration between science and society to find solutions to complex problems through collaboration and co-creation with and for society. The RRI Hub has therefore developed a structured community-building concept for regional and supra-regional ecosystems, which will be subject of the conference presentation. Our approach is that social innovations for complex problems can only emerge in lectures if the results are connectable. This can be achieved by involving qualified actors in the research, development and teaching process. In a multi-stage community-building process, actors were identified,

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² formulated within the excellence initiative

contacted and systematically integrated. Frequent communication with partners inside and outside the city has led to trustful collaborations from which both science and society benefit. We show how a successful community-building approach can look like and which challenges universities have to face in such processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century our society will face several ecological, economic as well as social challenges. Finding solutions for these challenges is crucial. As the actual COVID-19 pandemic drastically demonstrates these challenges formulated within the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are interfering and interacting in many dimensions [1].

Universities contribute significantly to the development of new innovations through their research and have a high innovation potential as the ranking of "Europe's Most Innovative Universities" shows [2]. These innovations are supported on the one hand by public funds of the government and on the other hand by industry-led third party funds. Successful innovations resulting from collaboration between universities, industry and government show what a successful technical innovation ecosystem can look like. The collaboration between these actors enables the development of innovations designed to meet the needs of the stakeholders involved.

But as formulated within the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) concept, technical innovations have to be developed with stakeholders from society in order to develop sustainable solutions that include ecological, economical as well as social perspectives. RRI's rationale is "that science and technology have the power to transform the future, that they are socially, ethically and politically entangled and that they can have potentially far-reaching, uncertain and unpredictable social consequences" [3]. Therefore, engineering sciences for example have to collaborate with scientists from other disciplines and with the involvement of society in order to create solutions that meet the needs of society. Various scholars state that social innovations can contribute to solving global challenges. Especially in the case of social innovation, collaboration with different actors and society is necessary [4]. The development of a social innovation ecosystem is essential and existing technical innovation ecosystems can be used as a starting point for their development.

However, various innovation models as the triple helix model fail to take civil society into account [5]. We argue that civil society as a driver of social change must be considered and involved in social innovation processes. In order to promote social innovation, universities need to develop a social innovation ecosystem and promote close collaboration with different stakeholders and especially with civil society. Since public support for this collaboration in the field of social innovation is low, universities must find their own ways to promote collaboration with civil society. Therefore, a systematic community-building approach is necessary.

Technical Universities as Drivers of Social Innovations

According to a report by the World Economic Forum, Germany was one of the world's most innovative countries in 2018. In particular, the report positively highlighted networks between research institutions and companies and the collaboration between various stakeholders [6]. In the field of technical innovation, technical universities are already collaborating with various actors. Technical universities thus already have an existing infrastructure to promote social innovation. In addition, many motivated students are involved in student associations and organizations alongside their studies and are already working on social innovations. Technical universities therefore already have the best conditions to promote social innovation and to act as drivers of social innovation. Social innovation processes, however, require the involvement of different actors and especially of civil society in order to represent the perspective of all members of the society. Nevertheless, many technical universities lack a systematic community-building approach to connect the various actors within the region. This paper presents a community-building approach for technical universities that considers the different actors within a region

2 METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

Within this paper we discuss the community-building approach developed at RWTH Aachen University - a leading technical university in Germany - as an example to illustrate how a regional community can be established between university, civil society and other actors with the aim of promoting social innovation. We show that building a trustful environment and a common narrative are important elements of community-building in higher education.

We first define social innovation and community-building. Taking into account the need and added value for universities by promoting social innovation and the collaboration between academia and diverse actors like civil society, industry or government, we describe our 4-step community-building approach at RWTH Aachen University, a regional embedded technical university in Germany. From this, we derive learnings for other universities, especially technical universities. We conclude by drawing out important implications for developing a supra-regional community-building approach.

2.1 Community-Building and Social Innovation at Universities

A social innovation community should involve actors from multiple areas with different competencies and skills [7]. Based on previous definitions (see [8]), we describe a community as a group of people including e.g. students, scientists, governmental actors and civil society who have a common goal (in our case "social responsibility and building an innovation ecosystem") and who join forces and support each other to achieve a common goal. Mulgan et al. [9] highlight the role of community development in social innovation processes [9]. Social innovations are created through collaborative teamwork, lead to a more inclusive society in the end describe an activity that contributes to solving social or societal problems [4]. The focus is on the satisfaction of a social need and the creation of added value for

society as a whole [9]. Various researchers assume that social innovation can lead to social change. However, this connection has not been widely explored [7]. The development of social innovations often takes place at the interface between different areas. Technical universities offer an existing organizational structure, motivated students and an existing platform that can promote an intensive collaboration between different areas to foster social innovation. In our knowledge society, science can play an important role in the development, testing and dissemination of social innovations. However, the results of a European study show that universities have not yet systematically engaged in the field of social innovation. Research and educational organizations were involved in about 21 percent of the social innovations [10]. Therefore, universities need to create appropriate structures to sensitize people to social problems and possible solutions and to promote the development of social innovations. An important condition is the establishment of a community that covers the broad range of all actors. Social innovations involving various actors and, in particular, society can only succeed if a community is established as a first step.

2.2 Four-Step Community-Building Approach

As one of the largest technical universities in Germany, RWTH Aachen University has recognized the importance of promoting social responsibility and social innovation. For this reason, the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) Hub was founded in 2019, funded by the Federal Republic of Germany and its federal states as part of the Excellence Initiative. The aim of the RRI Hub is to become a nucleus for a sustainable and socially responsible orientation of teaching, research and innovation. The RRI Hub is an initiator and platform for joint activities at the interface between science and society. For this purpose, the RRI Hub has successfully established a regional community in a first step. The aim is to connect people with similar goals and to contribute to a sustainable and socially responsible future through collaboration and co-creation. A requirement for building a community between universities and external actors is that this community should be based on reciprocity, interaction and mutual respect. Further elements are the participation of all community members as well as the establishment of a common decision-making process, whereby mutual respect between all actors is important [8]. Based on these community-building principles, a four-step community-building approach has been developed, applied and evaluated, as explained below and shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 4-step community-building approach for establishing diverse communities at technical universities

We used the quadruple helix model as the starting point of our community-building approach and identified the following four areas: government, academia, industry and civil society [5]. We used the model to establish a diverse community of actors, as the model made it easier to analyze the regional actor landscape and to quickly identify important actors in each area. Based on our regional approach, the helix government includes all actors employed by the city or involved in local politics. Academic actors are scientists on the one hand and students on the other. With regard to industry, we focused on regional companies in a first step while size and industrial sector were unimportant. Carayannis and Campbell [5] assume that well educated, well informed individuals form the fourth helix (civil society). In contrast to that, we defined the fourth helix involving the entire civil society. Our aim is to build an inclusive community of various actors, in which all individuals who share our interests can be represented. Therefore, only the engagement and interest are relevant, whereas social status, education, or age are no criteria used to build the community. To conclude, the fourth helix in our community-building approach

describes all persons in a society who are interested in collaboration between different actors in the field of social responsibility and innovation. Even though the RRI Hub as a project is located in academia, it initiates, connects and deploys a platform for actors across all areas. Based on our definition of the quadruple helix model, we collected different regional actors in each area. Through research on the internet and existing contacts, we collected all persons who might be interested in a collaboration in a first step. As this step served to collect all possible actors, no further criteria were applied.

We identified multipliers in all four areas in a second step (see Fig. b)). The reference point for the identification of the multipliers was the list of different actors, which we already collected in step one. We defined multipliers as individuals who are well connected within the region and who also have an interest in social responsibility and social innovation. The integration of multipliers allows us to balance communicational efforts. Multipliers assigned to the governmental area were mainly persons employed by different departments of the city. These included representatives from the municipal administrations in the fields of business, infrastructure and buildings as well as science. Academic actors were students and chairmen of student associations, members of the general student committee and scientists from different institutes. Particular emphasis was given to addressing interested students. Students do not only have expert knowledge but are also often active members of different associations and non-profit organizations and are already working on social innovation. Industrial multipliers included employees of regional companies with a focus on sustainability and the social sector. A further focus of our approach was on addressing multipliers from the civil society. For this purpose, we contacted actors involved in churches, foundations, non-profit organizations or associations. Once the multipliers had been identified, they were contacted.

In a first step, contact was established by e-mail or telephone. Subsequently, mostly personal meetings with the individual multipliers took place. These meetings served to get to know each other. Representatives of the RRI Hub as well as the multipliers presented the goals of their work and current projects. In most cases a first interlinking of the multipliers also took place. Suitable contacts from the RRI Hub community were shared with the multipliers, as well as they shared suitable contacts with us. Part of every conversation was the question of the assignment in the quadruple helix. Each multiplier was asked in which area they would assign themselves. One of the findings from the meetings is that the question of assignment into a single area is not appropriate. One example illustrates the problem: An entrepreneur whom we assigned to the "Industry" area and whom we initially contacted as an industry multiplier was also the chairman of a non-profit organization and thus assigned to the "Civil Society" area. Overall, we conclude that the assignment into single areas which we call static assignment is not appropriate in the field of social responsibility and social innovation. The engagement of many actors in the social sector is often independent of their actual profession.

Volunteering is the focus here as voluntary work usually takes place in addition to actual jobs in industry, government or science. Initially, civil society multipliers in particular had reservations about the work and objectives of the RRI Hub in terms of establishing and working with an equal community. Many civil society actors regarded the university as a closed system, which has no interest in opening up to society or collaborating with civil society. Actors regarded universities as a system in which a lot of expert knowledge is available, but often too little attention is paid to social issues. In a third step we therefore tried to reduce these reservations through trust-building activities.

Based on the findings of the second step, we abandoned the concept of static assignment and softened the boundaries of the individual areas of the quadruple-helix model in a third step to allow dynamic and cross-area assignment (see Fig. c)). In this third step, which we are currently working on, we concentrate on the consolidation of the existing network. So far, we have identified two important elements of a successful community-building approach: Trust and a common narrative. To create space for trust-building activities and to reduce the risk of a sense of competitiveness, the RRI Hub chose a two-staged communication approach. In stage one no public relations work of the RRI Hub took place. The focus was on addressing the multipliers and on the achievements and issues of the civil society actors. The official roll-out of the RRI Hub with the support of the multipliers is carried out in stage two. In this step, information about the RRI Hub is published on different websites. The multipliers will be given the opportunity to be presented on this website as well, in order to show mutual respect for the respective work. In addition, the activities will also be communicated via social media channels in the future, so that civil society in particular can access information more easily. The two-staged communication approach builds trust and provides the image of a non-dominant university. Moreover, we argue that trust can also be increased through mutual transparency and respect. For this reason, we regularly inform multipliers about current activities in telephone calls or personal meetings and inform ourselves about current activities of the multipliers. These discussions also serve to identify possible topics for collaboration. In consultation with the multipliers and based on our findings, the common narrative “building a social innovation ecosystem” was developed. The narrative serves to enable all community members to identify with an overarching goal. The common understanding of a narrative involving the multipliers in a common decision-making process has also contributed to building trust and respect.

The final step of our community-building approach is to establish a sustainable social innovation community with diverse actors. The networking of the various actors is the main focus. In addition to the networking of individual multipliers, several events and workshops will take place. Besides getting to know each other, the events will provide impulses for collaboration. Individual speakers or multipliers are invited to present their work, challenges and solutions. Even though all actors are from the

same region, the exchange of information between the individual actors is limited, although they basically pursue the same goals. The aim is to promote collaboration in various cross-area groups with different competences. At the end of step four, a sustainable social innovation community is to be created, which has an established communication structure between the individual areas and in which the RRI Hub acts as an initiator and research member. At the end of this last step of our community-building approach, the community must be known throughout the region and have a positive reputation, so that further multipliers become aware of the network and want to become part of it. The activities of the previous stages contribute to the popularity and reputation. In the end, the social innovation community will be independent of individuals in order to achieve a sustainable and long-term impact.

3 RESULTS AND LEARNING

This paper describes the development of a community at a technical university. Due to their established innovation infrastructure and numerous motivated students, technical universities have the best conditions to promote social innovation.

However, the promotion of social innovation can only be achieved in collaboration with various actors. For this reason, the first step is to build a diverse community. Therefore, the focus was on the development of a diverse community including civil society actors in order to consider the broad range of actors within a region. The described community-building approach has shown that the quadruple helix model must consider the entire civil society in order to cover the broad spectrum of all actors. Through various trust-building activities, it was possible to involve different actors in the community-building process and to establish a regional community. This community includes scientists, university staff, students and student initiatives, entrepreneurs, city employees as well as civil society actors such as chairmen of associations and foundations.

In discussions with multipliers, the academic ivory tower was a frequently mentioned point of criticism. Actors from civil society and government in particular criticised the fact that universities are not very open to society. Although universities often dominate the cityscape, they are considered a closed system that does not open up to society. Due to the specific terminology citizens feel not being able to understand what the universities are working on. Various actors were initially sceptical as to whether the RRI Hub wanted to establish a truly open and transparent cooperation. Dismantling this scepticism was one of our biggest challenges in establishing the RRI Hub. A successful community-building approach must be able to resolve this. We were able to identify two elements as particularly helpful: trust and a common narrative. Mutual trust has been achieved through the regular exchange of information, mutual transparency and an appropriate two-staged communication approach. Using this approach has showed the partners that the university considers itself a partner at the same level and not as a leading actor. The following sentence served as the common narrative: "Building a social innovation ecosystem". This enabled all multipliers to identify themselves with a common goal.

Another learning refers to the assignment of multipliers within the quadruple helix. The static assignment into individual areas in the quadruple helix is not appropriate in the area of social responsibility and social innovation. The engagement of actors in the social field is often independent of their actual profession. We argue that dynamic assignment is more appropriate as it should be possible to assign actors to multiple areas, since many people work on a voluntary basis in organizations in addition to their actual job.

Overall, our results show that the described community-building approach was successful at a regional level. With our approach we have covered the broad range of actors within a community and have also been able to convince those actors who are sceptical towards universities. This can be seen by projects which have already been successfully realized. One example of the successful cooperation with different actors is Aachen's joint application for the "Engagierte Stadt" programme. Together with the city administration, the student committee and a regional foundation, the RRI Hub will test and establish concepts for the promotion of social innovation within the programme. Another first success is the commitment to a joint campaign as part of a sustainability week and the joint establishment of a living lab run in collaboration with city stakeholders.

One limitation of our results is that the community-building approach has so far only been applied at regional level. Due to possible regional differences, the approach may have to be adapted for technical universities in other cities. In a next step, this approach will be transferred to the supra-regional level. One challenge could be that trust-building at a supra-regional level is considerably more difficult due to existing distances and cultural differences that could hinder regular personal communication. An adjustment of the approach is therefore assumed and will be analyzed in more detail in future research. In addition, further studies should examine the extent to which an established regional community can contribute to the development of a regional social innovation ecosystem.

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